

THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL-PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract: the article discusses the theoretical and conceptual foundations of professional competence, and analyzes various relationships in the scientific field. It is used as a feature that describes specific activity requirements for the labor subject, or precisely, the subject's attitude to the specific aspects of the specific activity.

Key words: professional competence, professionalization, professional maturity, competence, information-communicative, instrumental competencies

INTRODUCTION

The process of interaction and mutual influence of personality and activity has a dynamic character, and this process is studied within the framework of the problem of the formation of an expert personality[1]. The concepts of "professional (expert)", "professionalization (professional formation)", "professionalism", "competence", "qualification" and "professional maturity" are considered an important point of study of this problem. It is known that the last concept ("professional maturity") is considered one of the important characteristics of a labor subject, and it is manifested as the process of formation (professionalization) of a specialist and its result ("professionalism", "competence", "qualification").

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The essence of the concept of "professional maturity" was studied in the researches of a number of world psychologists (Derkach, 2002; Derkach, Zazikin, 1998; Zeyer, 2003; Noskova, 2000; Povarenkov, 1999; Rean, 2003; Tolocek, 2005)[2], but labor the formation process of these characteristics of the subject, the specific aspects of its manifestation in professional activity, and the characteristic aspects of the interaction of the formation of the professional personality with other components have not yet been sufficiently studied.

The concept of "personal maturity" is characterized by a high level of personal, psychological, social and professional development, in its adequate attitude to external reality, assimilation of spiritual-ethical, ethnic, cultural, professional and other standards, as well as standards of behavior in society, communication and consciousness, reflected in the manifestation of positive motives, value system, content and functional resources of the organism and psyche. This concept is widely used to describe a specific age period based on the specific characteristics of a person's development as an individual, a person, a labor subject.

Maturity is such a level of personal development that a person is able to fully fulfill his civil, family, professional and other obligations, as well as effectively participate in specific areas of society and work. "... the analysis of development shows that this process is extremely complex and contradictory: due to the different time taken for the development of different systems of the human organism to reach a high level, its psyche is very simple and very

complex, and the heterochrony of the beginning of its evolution and the speed of its passage inadequacy is observed" [3].

It is appropriate to consider professional maturity as a process of formation of a professional personality and professional formation of a labor subject. This process is related to the management and implementation of labor activities, but it is not limited to the development of the operational field, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also the research of S. L. Rubinshtein, B. G. Ananyev, B. F. Lomov, A. N. Leontiev and others. is related to the formation of a functional system of mental control of social behavior of a person. In this process, an important role is played by the development of ideas about the main laws of professional maturity of a person and the management of its dynamics under the influence of various factors, as a result of which a person begins to understand himself as a subject of professional activity and understands the level of social significance of his profession.

In the process of professional formation of a person, the goal orientation in the dynamics of revealing the essence of specific activity, the gradual discovery of its possibilities and the change of its individual components and structure is considered to be an important source. Determining, choosing, achieving a system of goals that require adequate activity in accordance with the psychological structure, and the content of individual activity components, as well as the degree of compatibility of mental tension to achieve the desired result, is also considered a source of mental development of a labor subject. This mechanism of development is the process of the formation and clarification of the motives of the subject activity, and the motivational needs that go through a specific phase of changes at each stage of the work process, enrich in terms of content and become the direction of activity, driving factors of mental and professional development. directly related to management.

The concepts of competence and competence are presented in the scientific works of scientists such as I.V.Petrova, YE.V.Sadon, O.YE.Gavrilova, A.V.Tarasova [4]. Also, in the UNESCO concept "The competent teacher 2010-2020", the modern interpretation of the concept of competence and its practical importance are highlighted [5].

Aspects of education of professional competences of specialists by pedagogical scientists of Uzbekistan .Researched by Khoshimova [6]. The widely used concept of "competence" is a criterion for evaluating professional formation and professional maturity, which does not yet have a clear definition. It is used as a feature that describes specific activity requirements for the labor subject, or precisely, the subject's attitude to the specific aspects of the specific activity. In general, this concept is characterized by a person's authoritarianism in certain life situations, social and professional activities, understanding and knowledge in this field. According to A.K. Markova, the competence of a certain person is a description that is more common than his professional formation. Accordingly, different types of professional competence can be distinguished: special (in the implementation of the work process), social (in the implementation of collaborative activities), personal (possession of self-management and improvement skills), etc. Some authors also highlight the competence in professional communication and the development of a specialist's personality.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Three main types of competences are distinguished:

1. Professional competencies refer to a person's field of professional activity. Among them can be included:

(basic general professional knowledge, skills and qualifications related to the field of professional activity;

(professional knowledge, skills and qualifications related to a specific field of modern production;

(special professional knowledge, skills and qualifications related to a narrow (specific) field of professional activity.

2. Competencies that need to be acquired quickly refer to social, communicative, methodical and other competencies necessary for effective work in various professions and fields of activity. Currently, among the skills that need to be quickly acquired are the skills of being able to participate in the organization of the workplace and the development of the enterprise; effective communication skills with colleagues, management and customers; competence to ensure the safety of vital activities; finally, qualifications related to the field of environmental protection are introduced.

3. General, basic or basic competencies are necessary for acquiring new knowledge and adapting existing knowledge to the new requirements of the labor market. The following competencies can be included among them:

socio-economic competences: defining and implementing prospective directions of self-intellectual, cultural, moral, physical and professional development and improvement; able to work independently in a team; critical analysis of accumulated experience; budget accounting; the ability to ensure the safety of one's life activity;

civil-legal competences allow orientation to society, awareness of one's rights and obligations;

informational and communicative competences, taking into account the opinions and views of other people; readiness for joint educational and educational-professional activities; readiness for indirect communication through a computer; ability to read and write in several languages; development of dialogic communication, discussion, including using Internet resources; is considered as the ability to read information from graphs, charts and tables;

instrumental competences to understand and propose ideas and thoughts for solving a human problem; use of techniques and technology in solving vital and professional tasks; communicative and linguistic skills in mother tongue and foreign languages; computer knowledge of information management, obtaining and analyzing information from various sources, organizing time and planning work; education is understood as the ability to build an environmental protection strategy [7].

The above-mentioned types of competence do not necessarily describe a person in their entirety, because a person can be a good specialist, but may not have self-management or interpersonal professional communication skills, and, moreover, a highly professional while having competence, personal and social competence may be low. It can be said that, in turn, the level of professionalism is determined by the subject's orientation, direction and content of professionalization, as well as the social, psychological, economic and other wide range of competences that affect the level of professionalization of the specialist.

Dj.Raven's research made it possible to base the structural-functional concept of competence, which is reflected in the following:

1. First of all, the importance of the systematic manifestation and formation of the sphere of personal motivational values, which determines personal values, socio-political trust and opinion.

2. Personal values are reflected in features such as direct interest in the organization and content of the work process, leadership, and organization.

3. The nature of competence is based on the criterion and manifestation of cognitive, emotional and volitional processes, the individual's readiness to solve and resolve issues that ensure the achievement of the goal.

4. Competence is formed not only at the expense of its active components, but also at the expense of passive components that can be manifested in new life situations.

5. Competence is determined by its numerous components, which are completely independent of each other, but can take the place of each other as factors of effective behavior. One of the important components in the implementation of innovations in the educational process in higher education institutions is the professional competence and innovative activity of a person. There are many approaches to the concept of "professional competence" in the science and practice of pedagogy. Professional competence as a term is often used in pedagogical, psychological, sociological and economic literature (S.Y. Batyshev, A.P. Belyaeva, V.P. Bepalko, E.F. Zeyer, N.V. Kuzmina, A.M. Novikov, A.K. Markova, I.P. Smirnov, E.V. Tkachenko, etc.) [8].

The research scientist E.F. Zeyer, who studies the functional development of professional competence, shows that various forms of competence become integrated during professional maturity and their connection with important professional personal qualities becomes stronger [9].

E.F. Zeyer stated that the study of the functional development of professional competence showed that various forms of competence become integrated during professional maturity and their relationship with important professional personal qualities becomes stronger [10].

According to K. J. Riskulova, "Competence" means a set of professional laws, principles, requirements, rules, duties, tasks and obligations, as well as personal deontological norms, necessary for the holder of this or that profession. Competence is related to the practical activity of a person, and it is the ability to demonstrate competence norms in work experience based on creativity based on the requirements of society. The main criterion of competence is determined by effective activity, training of competitive personnel" [18].

According to E.F. Zeyer, professional competence is a set of professional knowledge, skills, as well as methods of professional activity, which consist of the following components:

- socio-legal competence - knowledge and skills in the field of social institutions and human interactions, as well as professional communication methods and rules of conduct;
- special competence - readiness to independently carry out certain types of activities, ability to solve common professional problems and evaluate the results of one's work, ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills in one's specialty ;
- personal competence - ability to continuously improve professional skills and qualifications, ability to show oneself in professional activity;
- self-competence - to have a true vision of one's social and professional capabilities, to be able to overcome professional difficulties[12].

It is worth saying that the main levels of competence are professional training and experience, self-awareness, confidence in one's own strength, correct acceptance of shortcomings pointed out by other people, and other similar professional maturity of a person. features [13]. In particular, the basic levels of professional competence include professional training and experience, self-awareness, confidence in one's own strength, correct acceptance of

shortcomings pointed out by other people, and other such factors that determine professional maturity. includes personality traits.

M.I. Lukyanova divides professional-pedagogical competence into three structural components:

- 1) psychological and pedagogical literacy;
- 2) psychological and pedagogical skills;
- 3) a personal quality of professional importance.

At the same time, although it does not distinguish it as a separate component, the determination of professional competence considers the need to direct the student to pedagogical activity and the need for self-knowledge and change, to find a way to improve the activity in accordance with the change of the student's personality. shows [14].

In a number of studies, the professional competence specific to the pedagogue and its specific aspects have been studied. Among such studies, it is possible to include the research conducted by A.K. Markova and B. Nazarova. In her research, A.K. Markova notes that the professional competence of a pedagogue consists of the following structural foundations:

- special or professional competence (organization of professional activity at a high level);
- personal competence (self-development, self-expression);
- social competence (organization of additional activities in cooperation);
- individual competence (self-management, professional development and creation of innovations) [15].

The professional competence of a pedagogue and its specific aspects have been studied in the conditions of Uzbekistan, among which the research conducted by B. Nazarova is of particular importance. According to the researcher's opinion, the professional competence of a pedagogue is based on the following structural bases:

- special or professional competence (organization of professional activity at a high level);
- social competence (collaborative organization of professional activities, social responsibility);
- auto-competence (ability to develop oneself socially and professionally);
- extreme professional competence (ability to work in unexpected situations).

Z. Rakhimov believes that it is possible to make the following suggestions for the formation of the professional competence of the pedagogue:

- clearly expressed professional orientation, knowledge acquisition activity, manifested in the processing of acquired social experiences, inquisitiveness and creativity;
- development of scientific thinking, which creates a basis for making independent decisions in any non-standard situations that are common in professional activity, as well as for analyzing all the events and facts of the whole process;
- organization of independent education, which includes a wide scope, such as improvement of national and world pedagogical abilities, orientation towards self-development, development of research activities;
- organization of education that allows students to have their own individual styles in their mental and practical activities by individualizing the preparation of students for professional activities[16].

Professional competence refers to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. There are different definitions and approaches to this concept. According to N.M. Muslimov,

"competence" (incl. "competence" - "ability") means the effective use of theoretical knowledge in activities, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional qualifications, skill and talent [17].

CONCLUSION

Scientists are well aware that the suffix "-lik" in the term "competence" actually indicates the level of ownership of the quality of education. That is why this term is used in our national language and in pedagogical practice to define educational qualities and the level of their possession. Competence is understood as the integrated qualities of a person based on the knowledge and experiences acquired during the educational process, manifested in the general abilities to perform certain activities and his professional training.

References:

1. Бодров В.А. Профессиогенетический подход к проблеме формирования протии / Под ред. А.В.Брушленского и А.В.Карпова. – М: Ярославль: ДИАПресс, 2001. – С. 54-72.; Климов Е.А. “Как выбрать профессию” Москва, 1990.; Климов Е.А. Психолого-педагогические проблемы профессиональной консультации. М.: Знание, 1983. – 96 с.; Кондаков И.М. “Индивидуально - психологические особенности подростков в выборе профессии” Москва, 1989.; Кондаков, И.М. Методологические основания зарубежных теорий профессионального развития / И.М. Кондаков, А.В. Сухарев. // Вопросы психологии. – 1989. – № 5. – С. 158-164.; Сафин, В.Ф. Психологический журнал: Психологический аспект самоопределения личности 1984.
2. Деркач А., Зазыкин В. Акмеология: Учебное пособие. — СПб.: Питер, 2003. — 256 с.; Деркач А.А., Сайко Э.В. Субъектность субъекта в акмеологическом развитии и проблемы его субъектного самоосуществления.; Зеер Э.Ф. Психология профессий: Учебное пособие для студентов вузов. – 2-е изд., перераб., доп. – М.: Академический Проект; Екатеринбург: Деловая книга, 2001. – 149 с.; Волкова Е.Н. Субъектность педагога: теория и практика: автореф. дисс. ... докт. психол. наук. — М., 1998. — 42 с.; Прокофьева Т.В. Становление субъектности подростка в учебной деятельности: автореф. дис. ... канд. психол. наук. — Волгоград, 2001. — 19 с.; Кузьмина Н.В. Профессионализм личности преподавателя и мастера производственного обучения. — М.: Высшая школа, 1990. — 117 с.; Поваренков, Ю. П. Проблема индивидуально-психологического содержания профессионально важных качеств субъекта труда [Текст] / Ю. П. Поваренков. – Ярославский педагогический вестник. – 2008. – № 1. – С. 34–40.; Толочек В.А. Современная психология труда: Учебное пособие. — СПб.: Питер, 2005. – 479 с.
3. Жалилова С.Х., Хайдаров Ф.И., Халилова Н.И. Касб психологияси (ўқув қўлланма). – Тошкент, 2010. – Б. 67.
4. Петрова И.В. Формирование профессиональных компетенций у студентов вузов в ходе практикоориентированного обучения. / Дисс... канд. пед. наук. – Ульяновск, 2010. – С. 255; Садон Е.В. Профессиональные компетенции как фактор становления профессиональной карьеры будущего специалиста. / Дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. – Владивосток, 2009. – С. 218; Гаврилова О.Е. Формирование профессиональных компетенций студентовбудущих специалистов швейного производства в условиях

- образовательного кластера. / Дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. – Казань, 2011. – С. 257;
- Тарасова А.В. Физический практикум как средство формирования профессиональных компетенций студента медицинского вуза. / Дисс. ... канд. пед. наук. – М., 2012. – С. 249.
5. «The competent teacher 2010–2020», Tampereen Yliopistopaino Oy Juvenes Print, Tampere 2010.
6. Kadyrova M.T. The theory of competence approach and views on its pedagogical content. Molodoy uchenyy. 2020. No. 43 (333). - S. 343-345.
7. Исянов Р., Абдураимов Ш. Таълимга компетент ёндашув турлари. // «Барқарор ривожланишда узлуксиз таълим: муаммо ва ечимлар» халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман илмий ишлар тўплами. – Б. 225-227.
8. Корнеев Ю.В. Развитие профессиональной компетентности педагогов учреждений среднего профессионального образования. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата педагогических наук. – Москва, 2008. – С. 11. (- 23 с.).
9. Зеер Э.Ф., Шахматова Н. Личностью ориентированные технологии профессионального развития специалиста. – Екатеринбург, 1999.
10. Зеер Э.Ф., Шахматова Н. Личностью ориентированные технологии профессионального развития специалиста. - Екатеринбург, 1999. – С. 58.
11. Muslimov N.A., Muslimov Sh.N. Formation of professional competence in future teachers. // "Vocational Vocational Education" scientific-methodical journal, T., 2014, issue 5. - B. 30-31.
- Jalilova S.Kh., Khaidarov F.I., Khalilova N.I. Vocational psychology (study guide). - Tashkent, 2010. - B. 77.
12. Gulyamov K.M. The structural content of the professional competence of the future applied art teacher. Vocational education. 2020, issue 1. - B. 19-22.
13. Маркова А.К. Психология профессионализма. – М.: Знание, 1996. – С. 15.
14. Rakhimov Z. Pedagogical competence as an important factor in the development of the educational process. <https://cyberleninka.ru/>
15. Muslimov N.M. Fundamentals of pedagogical competence and creativity.
16. Riskulova K. J. System of formation of sociolinguistic competence of future English language teachers. Ph.D. (DSc) diss. the author. - Tashkent: 2017. - B. 14